

From Strategy to Implementation: National Cybersecurity Action Plan in Hungary

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Abstract

Hungary's experience offers lessons for any EU member state navigating the gap between cybersecurity strategy and implementation. The adoption of a new Cybersecurity Strategy (Government Decision 1089/2025) and a National Cybersecurity Action Plan for 2025–2030 marks a significant development in Hungarian cybersecurity governance. For the first time, strategic ambition is paired with a structured, publicly accountable implementation mechanism, addressing the strategy-implementation gap better than in earlier policy cycles.

This white paper examines the significance of the National Action Plan, the conditions necessary for its success, and the specific opportunity represented by Task 24 of the Action Plan: *the establishment of a professional forum to evaluate emerging cybersecurity technologies*. Task 24 addresses a structural failure in Hungary's technology adoption environment and is presented as a model deserving attention from Hungarian policymakers, EU institutions, and the defence community alike.

The Forum's priority technology areas are motivated by sovereignty concerns that rightly dominate both EU and Hungarian strategic discourse. Task 24 addresses three distinct theatres of engagement: infrastructure, data and cognitive. It suggests defensive tactics on each layer: Trusted computing environments, privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) and deepfake recognition tools, among others. Together these form a coherent sovereignty-oriented technology innovation agenda.

Keywords

Cybersecurity strategy, action plan, Hungary, NIS2, deepfake, content provenance, C2PA, SynthID, dual-use, civilian-defence cooperation, COcyber, Confidential Computing, Trusted Execution Environment, PQC, quantum resistant cryptography, privacy enhancing technologies, PET, technical sovereignty, data sovereignty, technology sovereignty, social resilience

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Table of contents

- Executive Summary 6
- 1 Introduction 6**
- 2 Updated Cybersecurity Strategy in 2025..... 7**
- 3 Policy Tools Context..... 8**
 - 3.1 The Strategy-Implementation Gap..... 8
 - 3.2 The Regulatory Environment 8
- 4 Cybersecurity Action Plan 9**
 - 4.1 Legal Status and Design..... 9
 - 4.2 Structure 9
 - 4.3 The Significance of the Action Plan for the Defence Community..... 9
- 5 Zoom In on Task 24: Emerging Technologies Forum 11**
 - 5.1 Mandate..... 11
 - 5.2 Problem Statement and Solution Approach..... 11
 - 5.3 Technology Selection Criteria and Priority Areas..... 12
- 6 Conclusions 13**
 - 6.1 Recommendations and suggested actions..... 14
- 7 References 15**

Executive Summary

Hungary’s 2025 Cybersecurity Strategy and its accompanying National Cybersecurity Action Plan (2025–2030) represent a shift from strategic ambition to structured implementation. By defining concrete tasks, deadlines, and responsible actors, the Action Plan directly addresses longstanding weaknesses in execution observed in earlier policy cycles [2][7].

Task 24 of the Action Plan introduces a notable governance innovation: the establishment of a professional forum for the cybersecurity evaluation of emerging technologies and cloud services. The initiative responds to a structural coordination failure in technology adoption, where regulatory uncertainty leads to a “mutual waiting” dynamic between regulators and market actors, slowing the uptake of strategically important technologies [1]. By creating a structured, expert-driven space for joint evaluation, the forum reduces uncertainty, supports trusted deployment practices, and enables progress in areas critical to digital sovereignty and competitiveness.

The technologies in scope—including trusted computing environments, privacy-enhancing technologies, synthetic media provenance, and quantum-resistant cryptography—address vulnerabilities across infrastructure, data, and the cognitive domain. These capabilities are inherently dual-use: the same tools that support secure civilian digitalisation are also relevant in defence contexts shaped by hybrid threats, cyber operations, and information manipulation [15][12]. The Task 24 Forum therefore provides a practical mechanism to strengthen civilian–defence cooperation in cybersecurity, aligning with the core objectives of the COcyber project. The Hungarian example represents a concrete best practice in defence–civilian collaboration that the COcyber project makes available to the wider community to support and promote knowledge exchange.

6

1 Introduction

Businesses cannot operate securely, citizens cannot engage confidently, and governments cannot deliver services reliably without a cybersecurity environment that matches the ambition of their digitalisation goals. Hungary has made significant commitments to digitalisation across government [14], healthcare [16], and public services [13], and the cybersecurity architecture underpinning those commitments must keep pace.

This white paper is produced in the context of the COcyber project and builds on the country case study on cybersecurity technology and information transfer (CCSH - Country Case Study for Hungary) [1], developed under Task D4.2. The CCSH provides the primary empirical foundation for the analysis presented here.

The paper examines Hungary’s 2025 Cybersecurity Strategy and National Cybersecurity Action Plan with a focus on implementation. It identifies Task 24—establishing a professional forum for

the evaluation of emerging cybersecurity technologies—as a key mechanism for addressing structural barriers to technology adoption.

The analysis is intended for three audiences: Hungarian policy actors responsible for implementation, EU institutions interested in transferable governance models, and the defence community, where the adoption of dual-use cybersecurity capabilities is essential for strengthening national resilience.

2 Updated Cybersecurity Strategy in 2025

The Cybersecurity Strategy of Hungary (Magyarország Kiberbiztonsági Stratégiája), adopted by Government Decision 1089/2025 [2] on 31 March 2025, covers the period 2025–2030. It supersedes not only the earlier cybersecurity strategy issued in 2013 [3] but also the network and information systems security strategy from 2018 [4]. The same Decision simultaneously mandated the preparation of a National Cybersecurity Action Plan, which is an implementing mechanism for the Strategy.

The twelve-year period between Hungary's first and second dedicated cybersecurity strategies included important regulatory developments, most notably the transposition of NIS2 [5] through Act LXIX of 2024 [6] and its implementing regulations.

The Strategy is structured around seven pillars: international cooperation; innovation and research and development; strengthening the legal and regulatory framework; strengthening the domestic organisational system; awareness, training and recruitment; promotion of cybersecurity certification; and protection of sectoral tasks and critical infrastructures. As documented in CESH [1], Section 2 — National Cybersecurity Strategy, these pillars collectively address the areas where Hungary's cybersecurity ecosystem has historically been weakest.

The Strategy explicitly acknowledges hybrid threats, addressing state-sponsored cyber operations and disinformation alongside conventional cybercrime, and linking to the National Military Strategy in its treatment of cyber defence obligations. Critically, the Strategy recognises that national cybersecurity cannot be achieved by the public sector alone. This is a promising improvement over the earlier approach which limited the cybersecurity policy discourse to governmental institutions and academia, without inviting businesses.

In efforts aimed at the cybersecurity of the country, it is not only possible but necessary to rely on actors beyond the public sector.

Cybersecurity Strategy of Hungary, 2025 [2]

These passages provide the direct mandate for the multi-stakeholder, private-sector-inclusive forum model that the Action Plan operationalises through tasks such as Task 24.

3 Policy Tools Context

3.1 The Strategy-Implementation Gap

Hungary has historically demonstrated strong strategic planning in cybersecurity but weaker implementation. Previous strategies were often not supported by clearly assigned responsibilities, measurable indicators, or effective monitoring mechanisms, limiting their operational impact. This pattern is reflected both in international assessments and in stakeholder feedback collected in the CESH [1], where several respondents characterised earlier strategies as having limited practical impact.

This assessment is consistent with broader governance findings. The OECD has noted that Hungarian public policy has historically been characterised by ambitious strategic planning without sufficient linkage to implementation mechanisms such as financing, accountability, and performance monitoring [18].

The 2025 Cybersecurity Strategy introduces structural improvement by mandating a National Cybersecurity Action Plan alongside the strategy itself. By defining concrete tasks, deadlines, and responsible actors, the Action Plan establishes an implementation framework that was largely absent in earlier policy cycles [2][7]. Its effectiveness will depend on sustained execution and transparent reporting.

3.2 The Regulatory Environment

The Action Plan operates within a more demanding regulatory environment shaped by the transposition of the NIS2 Directive through Act LXIX of 2024 [5][6]. This framework expands obligations, strengthens supervisory powers, and introduces stricter oversight mechanisms, increasing both compliance pressure and regulatory expectations.

At the same time, the regulatory environment is characterised by institutional separation between civilian and defence cybersecurity authorities. As documented in the CESH [1], this separation reflects genuine organisational and cultural differences but also creates coordination challenges in areas where technologies and threats span both domains.

The regulatory context is further shaped by the EU's evolving framework on artificial intelligence. Transparency requirements for AI-generated content under the AI Act [8][9] are directly relevant to emerging technology areas addressed by the Action Plan, particularly in relation to synthetic media and content provenance.

These regulatory and institutional conditions contribute to a coordination problem in the adoption of innovative cybersecurity technologies, reinforcing the need for mechanisms such as Task 24.

4 Cybersecurity Action Plan

4.1 Legal Status and Design

The Action Plan [7], published on the official website of the Government kormany.hu on 31 July 2025, is an administrative rather than normatively binding instrument; participation by non-governmental organisations is voluntary by design. The CCSH [1] found that informal professional forums outperform formal channels for genuine knowledge exchange in Hungary's cybersecurity community. Converting voluntary tasks into regulatory mandates would risk replacing expert contribution with formal compliance, undermining the collaborative quality that gives the forum model its value.

4.2 Structure

The Action Plan organises its tasks across eight chapters corresponding to the Strategy's pillars: strengthening international presence; enhancing innovation; strengthening the legal framework; consolidating the domestic organisational system; facilitating information flow and developing basic cyber capabilities; raising awareness and training the next generation; promoting cybersecurity certification; and sectoral cybersecurity tasks covering critical infrastructure. Task 24, discussed in detail below, falls under Chapter 4.

9

4.3 The Significance of the Action Plan for the Defence Community

The Action Plan is primarily a civilian instrument even though the defense sector is represented with a dedicated subsection within the Sectoral Cybersecurity Tasks chapter. The institutional separation between civilian and defence cybersecurity authorities established by the Cybersecurity Act [6] reflects genuine organisational and cultural differences between the two communities. The CCSH [1] documented these differences in detail: defence respondents emphasised formal institutional frameworks, federal obligations, and strategic stability, while market participants focused on operational efficacy and systemic deficiencies. Communication channels between the two communities were found to be primarily ad hoc or limited to a narrow subset of the two respective communities, without structured mechanisms for knowledge sharing. On a positive note, the Hungarian Defence Forces was relatively more open to cooperation than other institutions of defense.

Within this context of acknowledged institutional separation, there are nevertheless compelling reasons why the Action Plan, and Task 24 in particular, is significant for the defence community.

Shared challenges

Hybrid warfare, combining cyber operations with disinformation, influence campaigns, and other non-kinetic tools, cannot be addressed by either the civilian or defence sphere in isolation [15]. Countering Foreign Information Manipulation and Interference (FIMI) requires shared capabilities, situational awareness, and coordinated responses across both domains.

The Cybersecurity Strategy of Hungary explicitly recognises this interdependence, including through references to the National Military Strategy in its treatment of cyber defence. This reflects the reality that threats and attack methods increasingly transcend institutional boundaries. Incidents affecting Hungarian defence institutions further demonstrate that the same techniques—such as phishing, ransomware, and information manipulation—are used across civilian and defence targets [10][11].

At the same time, the modernisation of the Hungarian Defence Forces increasingly relies on cyber and digitally enabled capabilities [12], making the defence community a direct stakeholder in the same technology landscape that Task 24 seeks to address. The forum established under Task 24 should therefore be seen as a shared resource, supporting both civilian and defence actors in adapting to a converging threat environment.

Shared responsibility for sovereignty

Technology has become a key aspect of national sovereignty due to increasing dependency of national resilience on digital technologies and data.

The Strategy frames this with particular clarity:

Our sovereignty also depends on whether other countries can put the most advanced technologies and infrastructure to use more effectively than we can. Decisions that may, as a side effect, require us to forgo the most competitive forms of a modern technology must therefore be taken with particular care. Without adequate technological investment, our ability to leverage, in conflict situations, the comparative advantages we have built up against challenger states may be reduced.

Cybersecurity Strategy of Hungary, 2025 [2]

Task 24 responds directly to this imperative by showing that although powerful innovative technologies often raise legitimate security concerns, many of these risks can be mitigated with adequate defensive practices. That way the Task 24 Forum can contribute to high quality regulatory policies that balance the benefits and risks of the adoption of high-impact technologies e.g. artificial intelligence, cloud and quantum which deeply impact Europe's competitiveness.

5 Zoom In on Task 24: Emerging Technologies Forum

5.1 Mandate

Task 24 of the National Cybersecurity Action Plan [7] establishes a professional forum to accelerate the adoption of emerging cybersecurity technologies by resolving the regulatory and knowledge barriers that currently prevent their deployment. The forum is designed as a multi-stakeholder platform bringing together regulatory authorities, national security organisations, research institutions, technology providers, and user representatives to enable continuous, expert-driven assessment of relevant technologies.

Effective dialogue between market actors and public institutions is central to this mission. The Action Plan designates two coordinating organisations that reflect this duality: IVSZ (the Hungarian Association of Digital Companies), representing the digital economy and the private sector perspective, and HUN-REN SZTAKI (Institute for Computer Science and Control), representing applied research.

5.2 Problem Statement and Solution Approach

The CCSH [1] and the COCyber comparative analysis [19] identify regulatory uncertainty as a key barrier to the adoption of innovative cybersecurity technologies. In practice, this results in a coordination deadlock: organisations are reluctant to deploy technologies without clear regulatory guidance, while regulators are hesitant to issue guidance in the absence of established use cases.

This “mutual waiting” dynamic slows the adoption of technologies that are otherwise technically mature and widely used in international contexts. The effect is particularly pronounced in regulatory environments where compliance requirements are detailed and supervisory practices are strict.

Task 24 is designed to break this deadlock by creating a structured environment for joint evaluation. By enabling regulators, market actors, and researchers to assess technologies collaboratively, the forum reduces uncertainty on both sides: regulators gain insight into technological capabilities, while organisations gain confidence in acceptable deployment scenarios. This shared understanding supports both innovation and regulatory clarity.

This coordination problem is amplified by the Hungarian regulatory environment. The transposition of the NIS2 Directive [5] through Act LXIX of 2024 introduced a more prescriptive and supervisory-intensive framework than the Directive’s baseline, including detailed controls based on NIST 800-53 [17] and expanded supervisory powers [6]. While these measures strengthen security, they also increase perceived regulatory risk for organisations considering the deployment of innovative technologies not yet explicitly addressed in regulatory guidance.

This coordination problem is further reinforced by the dynamic nature of the Hungarian regulatory environment. The Cybersecurity Act (Act LXIX of 2024) and its main implementing regulation (Government Decree 418/2024) have both been amended multiple times within a short period following their adoption [6]. While iterative refinement is expected in a rapidly evolving policy domain, frequent regulatory changes can increase uncertainty among regulated entities regarding how requirements will be interpreted and enforced in practice.

In this context, organisations tend to prioritise compliance with existing obligations over the exploration of innovative solutions. Perceived risk of misinterpretation or non-compliance reduces willingness to adopt technologies that are not yet explicitly recognised in regulatory frameworks. As a result, regulatory dynamism, while intended to improve security, can inadvertently suppress innovation by increasing the perceived cost of experimentation.

5.3 Technology Selection Criteria and Priority Areas

Technologies considered within the Task 24 Forum are selected based on a consistent set of criteria: they remove barriers to important economic or scientific objectives, lack institutional ownership in Hungary, demonstrate established international use cases, function as enabling technologies, and face no explicit legal barriers to adoption.

Based on these criteria, four priority domains have been identified: trusted computing environments, privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs), synthetic media provenance, and quantum-resistant cryptography. These domains correspond to key layers of digital sovereignty—namely infrastructure, data, and the cognitive domain—where adversaries may seek to exert influence or gain unauthorised access.

The role of the Task 24 Forum is not to promote specific technologies, but to establish a shared professional understanding of their benefits, limitations, and conditions of deployment. This includes identifying use cases, clarifying acceptable implementation scenarios, and supporting the development of regulatory and supervisory practices aligned with technological realities.

The technologies in scope are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Task 24 Forum – scope of operation

Focus on:	Trusted application execution	Quantum computing	Content and information	Societal resilience
Theatre of engagement:	Infrastructure	Infrastructure	Data	Cognitive
Risk:	Untrusted cloud environments	Quantum computers break current cryptography	Traditional encryption cannot protect data while in use	Deepfake supported disinformation and fraud
Defensive tactic:	Cryptographic proof of environment	Quantum resistant cryptography	Encrypt in-use, pseudonymise	Help users recognise synthetic media
Technologies and capabilities in scope:	<p>Confidential computing: Encrypted in-use processing in trusted execution environments (TEE)</p> <p>Hardware security module: secure key management</p> <p>Sandboxes: Assurance through testing under controlled conditions</p>	<p>Post-quantum cryptography (PQC): Quantum-resistant algorithms for data transfer and storage</p> <p>Processes and methodology Audience-specific education, organisational readiness</p>	<p>Privacy-enhancing technologies (PET), incl:</p> <p>Differential privacy Statistical noise injection to prevent re-identification</p> <p>Federated learning Train models without sharing raw data</p> <p>Homomorphic encryption Compute directly on encrypted data</p> <p>Other relevant PETs</p>	<p>Content prove-nance C2PA: cryptographically signed metadata, verifiable chain of custody</p> <p>AI watermarking SynthID: invisible marks embedded at point of generation</p> <p>Deepfake detection: AI recognition of manipulated media</p> <p>Media literacy critical evaluation of digital content</p>

The cross-domain applicability of these technologies further reinforces their relevance in both civilian and defence contexts.

6 Conclusions

Hungary’s 2025 Cybersecurity Strategy and Action Plan mark a shift toward implementation-focused cybersecurity governance, with defined tasks, deadlines, and responsibilities addressing previous execution gaps.

Task 24 exemplifies this approach by addressing a coordination failure in the adoption of innovative cybersecurity technologies. By enabling joint evaluation among regulators, market actors, and researchers, it reduces regulatory uncertainty and supports the deployment of solutions relevant across civilian and defence domains.

The Hungarian model demonstrates the value of structured cooperation mechanisms in bridging the civilian–defence divide, offering a transferable approach for strengthening cybersecurity governance and supporting dual-use capability development.

6.1 Recommendations and suggested actions

For Hungarian government and policy actors:

1. Participation of institutions involved with cybersecurity in Task 24 Forum to gain direct insights into ideas and information relevant for developing their respective missions.
2. The National Authority for Data Protection and Freedom of Information (NAIH) is invited to participate in the Task 24 Forum. Privacy-enhancing technologies qualify as pseudonymisation techniques under GDPR, making their evaluation directly relevant to NAIH's regulatory mandate.
3. Ensuring that Task 24's outputs feed directly into supervisory practices of cybersecurity and data protection authorities (NAIH), including sectoral supervisors (NKI, SZTFH, MNB, HM). This would contribute to a supportive regulatory environment for carefully vetted innovations.
4. Authorities are invited to issue targeted guidance on innovative cybersecurity and information protection methods, leveraging the outputs of the Forum. For example, Regulation MK 7/2024 [21] provides for substitute measures (Sections 3 and 4 of Appendix 1) if the information system cannot implement the measures required in Regulation MK 7/2024, Appendix 2. Some of the technologies discussed by the Task 24 Forum could be applied as a substitute measure that achieves the same or higher control as traditional measures listed explicitly by MK 7/2024.

For EU institutions:

5. Hungary's Action Plan model merits documentation and dissemination as a potential template for supporting member states that face the implementation gap between EU cybersecurity objectives (NIS2 and beyond) and operational resilience. Incorporating it into ECCC capacity-building support programmes would extend its value beyond the Hungarian context.
6. Supporting cross-member-state linkages between national emerging technology evaluation forums, enabling shared assessments and avoiding duplication of effort, would extend the value of the Task 24 model to the EU level.

For the defence community:

7. Participating in the Task 24 Forum to leverage civilian-developed tools with direct defence relevance, without requiring formal co-participation in civilian institutional structures.
8. Leveraging Task 24 Forum engagements to identify partners and vendors with the potential to provide dual-use technologies.

7 References

- [1] COcyber Project. D4.2 National Case Study on Cybersecurity Technology and Information Transfer – Hungary (CCSH). 2025. COcyber Consortium. Available at: <https://www.cocyber.eu>
- [2] Government Decision 1089/2025. (III. 31.) on Magyarország Kiberbiztonsági Stratégiája. Nemzeti Jogszabálytár. <https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2025-1089-30-22>
- [3] Government Decision 1139/2013. (III. 21.) on Hungary's Nemzeti Kiberbiztonsági Stratégia. Nemzeti Jogszabálytár. <https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2013-1139-30-22>
- [4] Government Decision 1838/2018. (XII. 28.) on Hungary's Strategy for the Security of Network and Information Systems. Nemzeti Jogszabálytár. <https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2018-1838-30-22>
- [5] Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union (NIS2 Directive). EUR-Lex. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32022L2555>
- [6] Act LXIX of 2024 on Cybersecurity in Hungary (2024. évi LXIX. törvény a kiberbiztonságról). Nemzeti Jogszabálytár. <https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2024-69-K0-00>
- [7] Government of Hungary. National Cybersecurity Action Plan (Nemzeti Kiberbiztonsági Akcióterv) 2025–2030. Published 31 July 2025. <https://cdn.kormany.hu/uploads/document/a/a5/a55/a55d2e5d3162bf11474161023462b1dd471843d0.pdf>
- [8] Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (AI Act). EUR-Lex. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R1689>
- [9] Act LXXV of 2025 on the Implementation of the EU AI Regulation in Hungary (2025. évi LXXV. törvény). Nemzeti Jogszabálytár. <https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2025-75-K0-00>
- [10] Frész, F. CyberThreat Report. Ransomware támadás érhet a Védelmi Beszerzési Ügynökséget (2024). <https://www.cyberthreat.report/p/ransomware-tamadas-erhet-a-vedelmi-beszerzesi-ugynokseget>
- [11] Trend Micro. (2015). Operation Pawn Storm: Using decoys to evade detection. <https://documents.trendmicro.com/assets/wp/wp-operation-pawn-storm.pdf>
- [12] Kovács, L. (2021). Offenzív kiberműveletek II.: Kibererők és képességeik. Hadmérnök, 16(3), 119–137. <https://doi.org/10.32567/hm.2021.3.7>
- [13] European Commission. (2025). Hungary 2025 Digital Decade country report. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/factpages/hungary-2025-digital-decade-country-report>
- [14] Digitális Magyarország Ügynökség (Digital Hungary Agency). What we do - Digital Citizenship Program. <https://www.dmu.gov.hu/digital-hungary-agency>
- [15] NATO Headquarters Brussels, June 2024. Hybrid Threats And Hybrid Warfare Reference Curriculum. <https://www.nato.int/content/dam/nato/webready/documents/deep/Hybrid-threats-and-hybrid-warfare-ENGLISH.pdf>

- [16] Hungarian Ministry of Interior. (n.d.). E-Health Portal (EESZT Lakossági Portál).
<https://www.eeszt.gov.hu/hu/>
- [17] Government of Hungary. Regulation 7/2024 MK on the Classification of Electronic Information Systems and Applicable Protective Measures. Nemzeti Jogszabálytár.
<https://njt.hu/jogszabaly/2024-7-20-7G>
- [18] OECD (2015). Hungary: Towards a Strategic State Approach. OECD Public Governance Reviews, OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264213555-en>
- [19] COcyber Project. National case studies booklet on cybersecurity technology information transfer. COcyber Consortium. Available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/17972745>